

Data Handling Software
Documentation and Roadmap
Deliverable D4.3

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1 Abstract / publishable summary

Managing data from modern high resolution weather and climate simulations is becoming problematic. Here we present a summary of some of the middleware software developed within ESiWACE2 to help manage the deluge of data during and after simulations. Middleware is software that lies between the computer, network, storage fabric and the scientific code that exploits that fabric. The objective of the middleware developed here is to exploit some of the scientific knowledge we have about our data to more efficiently use the underlying fabric. To that end, we present a description of two classes of software which we have developed and/or improved during ESiWACE2: (1) Tools for in-flight analysis of ensembles of simulation which ideally can support cross-ensemble calculations, avoiding the need for writing all variables all the time or at analysis frequency for all ensemble members to disk; and (2) Middleware for managing writing data to disk and managing the migration of data through storage tiers. The particular products we discuss are XIOS and its ensemble analysis tools, the Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM), the Near Line Data System (NLDS) and tools which exploit the Climate-Forecast Aggregation conventions (CFA-C, CFA-Python, CFA-CPP and CFStore). Not all of these pieces of software are feature complete, but for each we discuss their current status, where to find code and documentation, and their roadmap to the future.

2 Conclusion & results

Two of the tools discussed here, XIOS and the ESDM, have a prime objective of facilitating output of data, but in their current incarnations, they have different secondary objectives. XIOS is being positioned to provide a full diagnostic sub-system and potentially even handle coupling, the ESDM is being positioned to handle the transparent migration of data between storage tiers (as might be necessary on an exascale system with burst buffers). XIOS is being deployed in a number of European models, but ESDM is only currently in use for testing, primarily because there were no systems available during the time of the project where we could fully test the ESDM (we had expected some to be available). XIOS is integral to ongoing activities, and the Unified Model based ensemble tools based on XIOS are currently being tested in a real science project. Furthermore they and are in heavy development for redeployment on another model, the UK NGMS. A number of projects in the UK and Germany are still investigating the utility of the ESDM.

The NLDS is a complete rewrite of the earlier product JDMA, in operation in the JASMIN data super-computer, with which we began ESiWACE2 and upon which we initially targeted our effort. But it became apparent that there were fundamental reasons why a rewrite was necessary. The new software is in testing and is intended to be operational at JASMIN by the end of 2023 (and is both available for porting elsewhere and relatively easy to port).

The semantic tools based on the Climate Forecast Aggregation (CFA) conventions are also in heavy development after a complete rewrite following experience during the first part of the project. There is significant ongoing funding for these tools, and they will be deployed within existing products such as CF-Python early in 2023, and new products, such as CFStore in later 2023.

3 Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action, primary contributions are shown with an X in the table below:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable
(1) Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021.	X
(2) Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available.	X
Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable
Boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre-exascale platforms	
Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling	X
Enhance HPC capacity of the weather and climate community	X
Improve the toolchain to manage data from climate and weather simulations at scale	X
Strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem	
Foster co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres	

4 Software products: statuses and roadmaps

This deliverable outlines the current state and deployment of the data handling software developed during ESiWACE2, provides pointers to the documentation, and summarises the road map for the future.

Note that the headline objectives for Work Package 4 (WP4) included:

1. To support data reduction in ensembles and avoid unnecessary subsequent data manipulations by providing tools to carry out ensemble statistics “in-flight” and compress ensemble members on the way to storage.
2. To provide tools to:
 - (a) transparently hide complexity of multiple-storage tiers from applications at run time by developing middleware that lies between the familiar NetCDF interface and storage, and prototype commercially credible storage appliances which can appear at the backend of such middleware, and;
 - (b) support manual migration of semantically important content between primary storage on disk, tape, and object stores, including appropriate user-space caching tools (thus allowing some portable data management within weather and climate workflows).

The work package had seven tasks, three of which were directly associated with producing software:

- Task 4.2, Ensemble Tools: The objective of the ensemble tools was to develop and deploy tools for controlling an ensemble of model instances within one executable feeding data output via an “active” IO server.
- Task 4.3, Earth System Data Middleware, ESDM: The objective of the ESDM task was to explore, harden, improve and evaluate the use of middleware which could exploit, but hide, storage system capabilities from the model using them.
- Task 4.4, Semantic Storage Tools: The objective of this task was to develop, integrate, and deploy tools which exploited knowledge of what data means to make efficient use of storage, in particular tape and object stores.

The first two of these correspond to discrete software which we discuss below in subsection 4.1 and 4.2 respectively. The semantic tools naturally split into two pieces, one to handle data migration, and one to use the semantic knowledge to do that migration, but as ESiWACE2 has progressed we have found it expedient to split the task into three: tape handling, aggregation handling (particularly for small files in object stores), and an integration layer. The first two of these have been discussed throughout our ESiWACE2 reporting, and are discussed in subsection 4.3 and 4.4, but the third is relatively new and is now much less mature. It is discussed in subsection 4.5.

We conclude this section with a summary of who did what, see subsection 4.6.

4.1 Ensemble tools

The primary objective of the ensemble tools is to allow ensemble statistics to be calculated for a set of model simulations being carried out simultaneously under one MPI communicator. We began with an initial prototype developed with UK national funding which exploits XIOS IO server, and aimed to extend that, making it more robust and suitable for wider deployment, including in demonstrator tasks in WP1.

The demonstrator task will be described elsewhere (ESiWACE2 Deliverable D1.3, due project month 50), here we concentrate on two major components of the resulting software: improvements in XIOS itself and the suites (workflow configurations) which handling failures within an ensemble member, ensemble diagnostics and the ensemble itself.

4.1.1 Status

XIOS stands for XML-IO-Server. This server infrastructure has wide applicability, and so a complete rewrite of much of the internal core engine has been undertaken utilising multiple funding sources on top of the ESiWACE2 investment. The work required for ensembles, and funded by ESiWACE2, forms part of that activity.

Over half of the relevant code (60000 code lines over 110 000) has been rewritten, with the goal to improve workflow performance and memory footprint impact, both of which are crucial to the use of XIOS for ensemble diagnostics. Other outcomes of that work included improved robustness and reliability of the code, a continuous integration test suite, graphical tools to visualize XIOS workflow filters orchestration and memory consumption, and better diagnostics of performance and memory footprint. The latter, together with more information (detailed stack traces) for XIOS errors is making working with XIOS ensemble development easier. A full description of the core rewrite will be found in Meurdesoif (2023, forthcoming) and in various presentations found at <https://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/ioserver>.

The workflow suites which handle XIOS based ensemble compression for the UM are described in Lawrence et al. (2018). The ESiWACE2 work has concentrated on improving these tools, adding test harnesses, making the suites easier to use, and adding new ensembles statistics, such as that shown in Figure 1. We have also had to implement the ensemble error handling in the suite control; as explained in D4.1 (Betke et al., 2021), we had originally anticipated a sophisticated solution to hand using MPI failure mode handling, but backed off to handling ensemble member failure in the suite.

Setting up the ensemble axis and the average operation on that axis:

```
<grid_definition>
  <grid id="um-atmos_grid_t_ufs">
    <domain domain_ref="um-atmos_grid_t" />
    <axis axis_ref="ensemble" />
  </grid>
  <grid id="um-atmos_grid_t_ufs_ens">
    <domain domain_ref="um-atmos_grid_t" />
    <scalar id="ensmean">
      <reduce_axis operation="average" />
    </scalar>
  </grid>
  <grid id="um-atmos_grid_t_ufs_1">
    <domain domain_ref="um-atmos_grid_t" />
  </grid>
</grid_definition>
```

Then the algorithm for the standard deviation which consists of a set of field definitions and an output file:

```
<field_definition default_value="-1073741824.0" prec="8">
  <field enabled=".TRUE."
    grid_ref="um-atmos_grid_t_ufs" id="m01s00i024" operation="average" />
</field_definition>
<file_definition format="netcdf4" time_counter="instant" type="multiple_file">
  <file description="UM_output" id="x2" name="ce262a_pc" output_freq="3h"
    split_freq="3h">
    <field field_ref="m01s00i024"
      name="m01s00i024" operation="instant" />
    <field field_ref="m01s00i024" id="m01s00i024_ens"
      grid_ref="um-atmos_grid_t_ufs_ens" operation="instant" />
    <field name="sqav"
      id="sqav" field_ref="m01s00i024_ens" > m01s00i024_ens*m01s00i024_ens
    </field>
    <field id="ensq"
      field_ref="m01s00i024" > m01s00i024*m01s00i024
    </field>
    <field name="avensq" id="avensq"
      field_ref="ensq" grid_ref="um-atmos_grid_t_ufs_ens" operation="instant" />
    <field name="stdev"
      grid_ref="um-atmos_grid_t_ufs_1"
      operation="instant" > sqrt(avensq - sqav)
    </field>
  </file>
</file_definition>
```

Figure 1: Example of the XML code used to calculate a standard deviation. The first step is setting up the XIOS axis and average reduction, then the standard deviation is calculated using a set of field operations and inserted into a file.

4.1.2 Code and documentation

XIOS documentation and code can be found at

1. XIOS documentation: <https://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/ioserver>
2. XIOS code: <https://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/ioserver/browser>, with current trunk <https://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/ioserver/browser/XIOS3/trunk>.

For the ensemble tools which utilise XIOS:

1. Ensemble test harness: https://github.com/NCAS-CMS/xios_test
2. UM suites which use XIOS for ensemble management: <https://code.metoffice.gov.uk/> (advice on how to get access can be obtained at cms.ncas.ac.uk, see also statement on open access to the suites in the roadmap below).

4.1.3 Industrial engagement

There is no third party industrial engagement in XIOS or the ensemble tools.

4.1.4 Roadmap

XIOS itself is subject to a continual process of improvement and the current version is “3.0 beta”¹. Full documentation of the internal ensemble support will be released as part of the XIOS-3.0 full release. As explained above, version 3.0 also includes a new internal services interface which will allow new ensemble management services, the actual implementation of those services will take part within a new French project called TRACCS (funded for eight years).

Within the UK EXCALIBUR ExcaliWork project, the UM ensemble suite has already been extended to support coupled ocean-atmosphere configurations; ExcaliWork will continue and take that work and apply it to the coupled configurations of the Next Generation Modelling System (NGMS) being developed for deployment on exascale systems. The NGMS code and hence the suites which use it, will have a very different license than that currently being used for the UM. So we expect that all the ensemble management code will at that point not only available on request, but available with completely open access.

A number of publications in various states of preparation, and will describe the entire development including the ESiWACE2 contributions.

4.2 Earth System Data Middleware

The ESDM² or Earth System Data Middleware can handle I/O efficiently and supports data storage for multiple backends. The flexible I/O semantics provided by ESDM simplify the mapping of datasets to multiple storage locations. ESDM is able to insert itself as an alternative middleware for an parallel application (and including XIOS) to provide improved performance by (1) changing the on-disk format of NetCDF; (2) by using runtime parameters and background threads to read/write data in large I/Os; and (3) by storing data on multiple storage systems at the same time.

4.2.1 Status

The development of ESDM can be considered to be in an extended beta phase. It has been used successfully in test cases but also in model runs using XIOS as will be described in the ESiWACE2 final report in section “Benchmarking OpenIFS with ESDM and XIOS” (this work being done now at GWDG).

¹<https://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/ioserver/browser/XIOS3/branches/xios-3.0-beta>

²<https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm>

Generally, we still advise for production run that it should first be verified that the generated output is correct and the toolchaining works as intended. In terms of development, the latest addition was the merging of fragments of a process in one POSIX object - this improved an observed performance degradation where too many objects have been produced. ESDM proved useful for the easy integration of additional and future storage interfaces as it supports various backends including PMEM.IO, MOTR, KOVE XPD, DDN WOS, S3, and for backwards compatibility POSIX file systems. ESDM served the purpose to explore additional features such as the on-the-fly data transformation - which has the potential to improve gradually the performance for subsequent reads following different access patterns. This feature remains in the alpha phase. The benefit of this feature can only be tested for multi-step workflows.

The actual observed performance gains over an existing solution, such as NetCDF and HDF5, depends on the test configuration and model output requirements. For configurations which are not I/O demanding (e.g., less than 1 GByte/s on 100 nodes), there is generally no I/O limitation to be observable and, thus, there is no need for ESDM and the ESDM won't improve performance. Unfortunately most production runs are configured in order not to be I/O bound (i.e. the I/O output has already been voluntarily limited by those configuring the run), so it is difficult to take an existing production run and evaluate the impact of the ESDM directly.

4.2.2 Documentation

ESDM itself is documented as part of the code³. The integration module in NetCDF is only partially documented but as it consists of one bigger C file in the repository⁴, the relation to NetCDF is apparent. The architecture of ESDM was introduced in Kunkel and Pedro (2020) and further developed in Deliverable D4.1 (Betke et al., 2021).

4.2.3 Industrial engagement

DDN and Seagate supported the development of ESDM and explored how to integrate it into their software distributions. The results of that work appear in D4.2 (Umanesan et al., 2022), the conclusions relevant to ESDM are repeated here:

- ESDM works with CORTX Motr from Seagate through the CORTX Motr API backend. The adaptation for ESDM on Mero (through the "Clovis backend") was implemented early on in the project and reported in D4.1. The Clovis backend was renamed to CORTX Motr API after it was open sourced. ESDM was hence made to work with that backend and proven in this deliverable.
- The CORTX Motr software with ESDM was successfully deployed on a virtual machine emulating commodity hardware and requirements at DKRZ - suitable for adoption by other weather and climate centres.
- DDN has ported ESDM on its IME flash native appliance. Obtained results on ESDM are extremely good: ESDM provides a semantic consistent with the expectations of scientists while achieving performance comparable to the one obtained with low level proprietary API from DDN.

4.2.4 Roadmap

ESDM as a basic product is completely implemented. The integration into actual production workflows is a key for adoption. Once used, potential performance limitations can be identified and overcome, also additional features such as the potential data transformations could be explored and utilized. The ESDM is being further evaluated and compared alongside other solutions such as the US ADIOS2 middleware (Godoy et al., 2020)

³<https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm>

⁴<https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm-netcdf-c>

as part of the UK ExcaliWOrk project. The ESDM will also remain a vehicle for subsequent I/O research of the High Performance Storage research group⁵.

4.3 Tape systems: from JDMA to the NLDS

During ESiWACE and ESiWACE2 the Joint Data Migration App (JDMA) was developed and deployed at UKRI Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA), and several years of experience were gained. While it significantly improved on the previous tape interface it had a number of flaws, and work on a replacement, the Near Line Data System (NLDS), began in ESiWACE2. The objectives of the NLDS were multifaceted, but included a need to vastly improve responsiveness and information management, and to be more easily redeployable.

The NLDS is a multi-tiered storage solution which is designed to use object storage as a front end to a tape library. Users interact with NLDS via a HTTP API, with a Python library and command-line client provided to support both programmatic and interactive use. When a user transfers files to the NLDS, the files are first written to the object storage, and in the next version a backup will be made to tape. When the object storage is approaching capacity, a set of policies will be interrogated to determine which files will be removed from the object storage. When a user retrieves a file, the NLDS may have to first transfer the file from tape to the object storage. This in effect creates a multitier of hot (disk), warm (object storage) and cold (tape) storage, with a common interface to all. While systems like this are not necessarily novel, the system developed here is Open Source, designed for ease of redeployment elsewhere, and for use from both local storage and remote sites (i.e. across a wide area network). It is designed from the off to work with a higher-level semantic layer.

In this section we describe the current status for each of the JDMA and the NLDS.

4.3.1 Status

The JDMA is the operational interface at JASMIN, providing user the ability to migrate data between disk and tape. It is slated for retirement as soon as the NLDS is ready to replace it.

NLDS development is progressing rapidly, now that the fundamental microservice architecture is in place. That architecture includes a message exchange broker and the HTTP API and storage solutions. The microservices consist of file scanners, a file transfer service, a cataloguer to record the files in the system, a system logger, and a monitoring service so that users can keep track of their transfers. The system is deployed via Kubernetes, with each microservice contained in its own Docker container, allowing the number of services to be scaled up or down, depending on the current load of NLDS. The design provides a scalable, yet power efficient, system with the use of a message broker ensuring that no communications between microservices are lost. OAuth is used to authenticate and authorise users, with a pluggable authentication layer allowing other methods to be added if necessary. The system can support both local and remote cloud-based services accessing the data via a URL, so long as the user has the required credentials (avoiding the necessity for a local file system mount).

Currently the use of the NLDS to migrate data to and from the object store cache layer is being developed and bugs and functionality around user interrogation are being addressed, details of the process can be seen at <https://github.com/cedadev/nlds/issues>. There is an aggressive timeline to get the NLDS deployed, as JDMA performance is not fit for purpose.

4.3.2 Code and documentation

All documentation and code is on GitHub:

1. The JDMA:

⁵<https://hps.vi4io.org/>

- (a) JDMA system: https://github.com/cedadev/django-jdma_control
- (b) JDMA client: https://github.com/cedadev/jdma_client
- (c) JDMA user documentation: https://cedadev.github.io/jdma_client

2. The NLDS:

- (a) NLDS server: <https://github.com/cedadev/nlds>
- (b) NLDS client: <https://github.com/cedadev/nlds-client>
- (c) User focused documentation for the NLDS is not yet available.

4.3.3 Industrial engagement

There is no direct industrial engagement in this project, although the team is tracking what industry is doing in this space.

4.3.4 Roadmap

The current NLDS timeline is shown in Figure 2. The CFStore team (see subsection 4.5) are beginning to work with the current version in the expectation that semantic layers will be deployed in parallel during late 2023. This work has been co-funded by CEDA throughout, and CEDA will continue to fund it after the end of ESiWACE2.

Figure 2: NLDS timeline as of the Milestone-4 meeting, late 2022. Note that many of the NLDS milestones were accompanied by stakeholder presentations which are available in Zenodo and given in Table 1.

4.4 Semantic tools: building on the lessons of S3NetCDF

S3NetCDF⁶ is a software package developed during the first ESiWACE project which was significantly updated during ESiWACE2. The aim of this package is to provide a drop-in replacement for `netcdf4-python` which could efficiently exploit NetCDF files stored in S3. When the project began there was no other way to do this, and little community experience of how best to use S3.

⁶<https://github.com/cedadev/S3-netcdf-python>

4.4.1 Status

We learnt a lot building S3NetCDF, but as of the end of 2022, there is both much more experience in the weather and climate community around using S3, and several other more performant tools which can exploit S3 (including Zarr and a version of the NetCDF library itself), so continuing the development of S3NetCDF on the original path has been halted. The effort we would have used on that has primarily been redeployed on using the lessons from S3NetCDF to inform a new version of the Climate Forecast Aggregation (CFA) Conventions, and to develop tooling which can exploit this convention, which could then be used by any tools which exploit NetCDF aware S3 interfaces. We will continue to develop S3NetCDF as one such tool, but our ongoing development of S3NetCDF is likely to be more focused on using it as a test harness for lower layers in the stack than on expecting wide usage of S3NetCDF itself. This work is now continuing in a UK funded project described in subsection 4.4.4.

The key ideas and motivation behind this are discussed in a technical blog article (Massey, 2021), but the important concept revolves around considering atomic datasets (one variable at one frequency from one simulation) as consisting of fragments (files or objects) each of which may consist of one to many storage chunks⁷. In the Zarr view of the world, fragments and storage chunks are usually synonymous, but in the NetCDF world we typically want multiple storage chunks per fragment and in the “science” world we want catalog entries to deal with atomic datasets and hide details of fragments and files.

CFA aggregation addresses hiding fragments so users only have to deal with “aggregation” views. While other tools can do this, none have published a specification so that multiple different tools can share persistent aggregation views. The CFA specification addresses this. The current implementation of S3NetCDF used an older version of CFA, and ESiWACE2 work made it clear that it was not fit for purpose, and so we have developed a new specification. In order to make it easier for other tools to utilise this aggregation we have developed a C-library implementation of basic tools for manipulating such aggregations (CFA-C) and two implementations of that in higher level library (Python and CPP). We are in the process of developing our own tools which can then use these. Beginning with CF-Python, future work will address the reimplementations in S3NetCF, but likely as a test harness rather than a tool for wide deployment.

4.4.2 Code and documentation

All this work is documented in GitHub:

1. CFA Conventions Document: <https://github.com/NCAS-CMS/cfa-conventions/blob/master/source/cfa.md>
2. CFA-C: <https://github.com/cedadev/CFA-C>
3. CFA-Python: <https://github.com/cedadev/CFA-Python/>
4. CFA-CPP: <https://github.com/cedadev/CFA-CPP>
5. S3NetCDF: <https://github.com/cedadev/S3-netcdf-python>

4.4.3 Industrial engagement

There is currently no direct engagement with the code stack, but the ideas are to be implemented with industrial partners (DDN and the UK SME StackHPC) as part of the UK ExcaliWork (exascale workflow) project.

⁷Storage chunks are used to make accessing regions of multi-dimensional data more efficient.

4.4.4 Roadmap

CFA-C is approximately feature complete. UK funding is being used to rework CF-Python so it can utilise DASK (and enter the Pangeo stack). That work is due for completion end of Jan 2023, and immediately thereafter CFA-C support for the latest CFA convention will be introduced into CF-Python. At that point we will have a high level tool with complete support for utilising S3 data in a very simple way. This will be the inheritor of the original S3NetCDF objective.

We have started discussions with Unidata as to the possibility of incorporating CFA-C in the NetCDF-C stack itself, with considerable community support for the idea from a meeting held in 2021. This will likely happen, if it happens, in the 2024 time-frame towards the end of the UK ExcaliData series of projects.

A number of other projects have spun up from the atomic dataset implementations we worked on with S3NetCDF, one of which is CFStore, discussed next.

4.5 CFStore

The work on NLDS and CFA, CF-C, S3NetCDF provide firstly, a system for managing files, and a system for managing and exploiting aggregations of files. The remaining necessary layer is something which puts those two things together.

We start by assuming that a simulation dataset will consist of several output atomic datasets, each of which is actually stored in many NetCDF files. The objective of CFStore is for the user to be relatively ignorant about the number and location of the individual NetCDF data files within all of the atomic datasets associated with a simulation - and to allow different parts of simulation atomic datasets to reside on different storage tiers within an institution or even across institutions. For example, CFStore must allow the system to know that part of the output of a particular simulation is still on an HPC platform, part is on a data analysis system like JASMIN, and some of it has been extracted and downloaded onto a local server or laptop.

This vision requires an “atomic dataset index” which actually knows where all the individual files are and how they are linked together. CFStore is an integration layer which aims to meet that objective, but it does much more, allowing users to tag, annotate, and add metadata to collections of atomic datasets. It is implemented as a “personal database” allowing anyone anywhere to import information about data anywhere they have ssh based login credentials.

The current state of CFStore is that is much less mature than the other items of software discussed here and so we do not provide the same level of detail as the other components. However, it is crucial to the eventual full exploitation of the ESiWACE2 goal of exploiting semantics to manipulate data within a storage hierarchy.

There are other tools which meet some of these objectives, but the big difference in CFStore is that it will fully exploit the Climate Forecasting conventions and aggregation conventions in the management of information.

The software and plans are available at <https://github.com/NCAS-CMS/cfstore>, and ongoing development is funded through to mid-2024 as part of the UK EXCALIBUR ExcaliStore project.

4.6 Effort

The work on XIOS was carried out at IPSL (by Meurdosif) and the work exploiting XIOS for ensembles at NCAS and UREAD (by Lawrence, Lister, Cole, Wilson, Pedro). The work on the ESDM was carried out primarily at UREAD (by Kunkel, Lister, Pedro) and the University of Göttingen (GWDG) under subcontract from DKRZ after Prof. Kunkel moved there from UREAD during the project. The work on the NLDS and most of the ESiWACE work on semantic tools was carried out UKRI STFC (by Massey), with leadership and guidance from UREAD (by Lawrence). The work on the test harness at ICHEC (see section 6) was led by McKinstry.

5 References

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6 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered

- An original objective was to provide support for climate ensemble compression building on work carried out for NWP by ECMWF, but early on the project the 1PM ECMWF effort to support this objective was moved elsewhere in the project and we dropped this task from ESiWACE2.
- Some of the planned developments of tools to support ESDM use did not happen as Professor Kunkel moved to Germany (University of Gottingen, GWDG), resulting in a long period during which he was not available. His ESiWACE2 funded PDRA remained at the University of Reading, and was re-deployed to advance the ensembles work. Some work was then moved to GWDG under subcontract to DKRZ, and as it is still ongoing, will be described in the ESiWACE2 final report. However, the core ESDM functionality was completed, and documented (D4.1) and industry implementations delivered (D4.2).
- We had expected to be testing the ESDM in real science examples on pre-exascale platforms, and some of that was done, but in the event the platforms were late. In particular, we had hoped to be using the UK ARCHER2 burst buffer storage for ESDM evaluation, but ARCHER2 was heavily delayed and the storage system is still not ready to test the use of the ESDM writing to multiple storage systems as a model runs.
- The continuous integration work that was planned was severely curtailed as ESDM development was scaled back during the project in favour of ensemble testing when Prof. Kunkel moved to Germany. A

test harness for the ESDM was built into an EC-Earth test flow, and GitHub actions are being deployed in some of the semantic tools, but given the major rewrites in the other tools, a full integrated testing system was not appropriate. However, recognising that testing I/O systems is an ongoing requirement, a new testing system designed for initial use on CASPIR⁸ has been architected. It will utilise the “Earth Observation Exploitation Platform Common Architecture” EOEPCA⁹, which is under development at ESA (including ECWMF and EUMETSAT). Support will be provided to kick-off or monitor EC-Earth dockerised jobs on the HPC node, with underlying NetCDF storage. This should then make the CASPIR implementation drop-in compatible with the “European weather cloud”, enabling Digital Twin work at ICHEC (e.g. bursting DTE/DestinE jobs to ICHEC, doing national-level projects that are portable from CASPIR to ECWMF/ESA, etc). This system will be capable of testing both future versions of ESDM and other I/O middleware products.

- Similarly, the workflow enhancements could not be completed while Prof. Kunkel was in transit. A paper on the architecture and initial investigations was produced (Kunkel and Pedro, 2020), and there was an investigation of potential performance gains before Professor Kunkel's departure, but initial investigations were unable to be completed.
- While the initial goals for S3NetCDF were met, the actual performance was not as good as expected and other performant products have appeared, including an unanticipated extension to NetCDF itself. Our original plan was to address that performance, but the work to do that would have been quite significant. Given other tools existed, we chose instead to take the learning, and in particular the learning around aggregation, and apply it to other parts of the problem space, hence the new tools discussed in subsection 4.4.2 above. These are not yet at a suitable technology readiness level to enter scientific workflows, but in all cases ongoing funding is in place, and operational deployment in real science projects is planned within the next eighteen months.

7 How this deliverable contributes to the European strategies for HPC

The drive towards high resolution and large ensembles is resulting in very large volumes of data. It is not possible to fully utilise exascale and pre-exascale systems without suitable I/O servers and middleware, without systems to manage the number of data entities being produced, and without tools for analysis at scale. This deliverable addresses all these issues, but does not provide a complete solution for any of them. There is much yet to do.

8 Sustainability

Most of the activities and components are either targeted for operational delivery within “business as usual” e.g. NLDS, XIOS ensemble services, embedding CFA within the maintained tool CF-Python. Others are still being project funded as they are not ready for wider use.

⁸https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/eurohpc-joint-undertaking-announces-five-sites-host-new-world-class-supercomputers-2022-06-15_en

⁹<https://eoepca.github.io/>

9 Dissemination, engagement and uptake of results

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

We ensure the uptake of the deliverable by the targeted audience through the following actions

- Ensembles: XIOS support for ensembles will form part of XIOS documentation and will be written up during 2023. The main engagement is between the engineers responsible for developing XIOS and those using it in models. The next step is to show successful outcomes from the science project using XIOS, then we would want to promulgate more information on the advantages of using the ensemble technique.
- Tape Systems: When the NLDS is closer to operations, or in operation, we will use appropriate European conferences to publicise what it is and how portable it is.
- Semantic Tools: We introduced CFA at the annual Climate and Forecast Conventions Workshop in 2021¹⁰, and will continue to advertise it there. Once we have a DASK and CFA enabled CF-Python we plan to show the capabilities in the Pangeo community at appropriate conferences, and work towards harmonising the methods of persisting aggregation descriptions.

When these tools reach suitable maturity and we have application examples, we will write formal descriptions in the academic literature.

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

See Table 1 and Table 2.

9.3 Publications in preparation or submitted

See Table 3.

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

All code created and described within this deliverable is in the public domain and uses standard open source licenses. Commercial experimentation with this software is described elsewhere.

¹⁰2021 CF Workshop: 21-23 September 2021 (virtual), <https://cfconventions.org/Meetings/2021-Workshop.html>

Table 1: Record of dissemination / engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached
Code in public repository	Release candidate 1 for S3-netCDF-python library	03/03/2021	Technical	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4575716	84
Presentation	"CFA-C A low-level interface to the CFA Conventions", milestone presentation to CEDA staff and stakeholders	25/04/2022, (UK)	Technical	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6576481	10
Presentation	"Progress on the Near-Line Data Store", milestone presentation to CEDA staff and stakeholders	20/01/2022, (UK)	Technical	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6576491	10
Presentation	"NLDS - Milestone 4 review", milestone presentation to CEDA staff and stakeholders	07/12/2022, (UK)	Technical	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7529561	10
Presentation	"NLDS - Milestone 3 review", milestone presentation to stakeholders	01/11/2022, (UK)	Technical	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7529551	10
Presentation	"The Near-line Data Store", knowledge exchange and progress meeting	10/11/2022, STFC (UK)	Technical	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7529580	20

Table 2: Record of dissemination / engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached
Presentation	"CFA library implementations", knowledge exchange and progress meeting at NCAS-CMCS	06/10/2022, Reading (UK)	Technical	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7529509	10
Blog post	"The Near-line Data Store"	09/03/2022	Everyone	https://techblog.ceda.ac.uk/2022/03/09/near-line-data-store-intro.html	> 1000
Presentation	"NetCDF Climate and Forecast Aggregation (CFA) Conventions", 2021 CF Workshop	23/09/2022	Technical	https://drive.google.com/file/d/10QwzgLNGd9-H10aWPkkio_4NRJSavxw/view?usp=share_link	10

Table 3: Publications related to this deliverable

In preparation or submitted?	Title	All authors	Title of the periodical or the series	Is/Will open access be provided to this publication?
Submitted	Potential of I/O aware work-flows in climate and weather	Kunkel, J.M. and Pedro, L.R.	Supercomputing Frontiers and Innovations	Yes
In Preparation	XIOS development – PART A: XIOS new release	Meurdesoif, Y.		Yes